

Real-Time Leakage Zone Detection in Water Distribution Networks: A Machine Learning-based Stream Processing Algorithm

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Abstract. This work presents LEAKSTREAM, a novel approach for detecting leakages in water distribution networks by leveraging the power of clustering and stream processing techniques, combined with advanced machine learning approaches. Given the critical importance of efficient water management and the significant economic and environmental consequences of undetected leaks, it is crucial to develop innovative strategies that can accurately and promptly identify anomalies within distribution networks.

Our proposed method focuses on an algorithm that creates clusters of nodes in the water distribution network, taking into account their spatial proximity and hydraulic characteristics. We employ stream processing to efficiently handle large-scale real-time data generated from meters installed at consumer locations throughout the network.

The results of our study indicate that the proposed leakage detection algorithm effectively employs a generalization technique to detect events not included in the training data. We show performance in terms of precision and loss in the case of 75 different leakages positions in a water distribution network which extends in an area of 7×3.5 sq km. Furthermore, its capacity to process data at the edge and in real-time enables prompt responses and mitigation measures, thereby reducing the overall impact of leaks on both the environment and infrastructure.

Our results attain an average accuracy of detecting and localizing the zone of the leakages of about 98.6% when leakages are not present during the training of the ML models.

Keywords: WDN, IoT, leakage detection, stream processing, k-means clustering, LoRaWAN, neural network

1 Introduction

Worldwide water consumption is consistently increasing, with demand growing annually. Additionally, considering the issue of climate change, the globe is confronted with an anticipated 40% water deficit by 2030 [1]. For this reason, the optimization and digitalization of Water Distribution Networks (WDNs) are becoming key objectives in our modern society.

In recent years, the increasing availability of data from water meter sensors, coupled with advancements in data processing and Machine Learning (ML) techniques, has provided new opportunities for enhancing leakage detection capabilities. Data-driven approaches can significantly improve conventional methods by providing more accurate, timely, and scalable solutions. Moreover, emerging IoT Low Power Wide Area Network (LPWAN) technologies, together with ML solutions, can help monitor water consumption and automatically detect leakages. In this paper, we leverage stream processing combined with IoT and ML to deploy a smart and innovative leakage detection method in a WDN.

This paper proposes LEAKSTREAM, a new solution to improve monitoring, leak management and prediction by exploiting stream processing capabilities in LPWAN networks. Our approach supposes to use common IoT water sensors placed at the utility consumers, used to measure user water consumption and ML algorithms to process the data directly at the edge of the network in order to detect leakages. Our solution is a Supervised Classification problem where we attempt to predict if there is a leakage in a zone of the WDN. We propose a methodology to detect leakage events in a distributed way by running ML algorithms at the edges of the communication network, and we use k -means clustering and neural network models for leakage identification. Finally, we present case studies that demonstrate the practical benefits and effectiveness of data-driven approaches in a simulated scenario that reproduces a real-world WDN. The innovative aspects of this work are the following:

1. We present and validate a learning-based for smart WDN, named LEAKSTREAM, which leverages the measurements of user utility demand and pressure to detect leakages in WDN.
2. We propose an original algorithm, encompassing WDN and IoT network scenarios, including a stream processing framework. The algorithm extracts "*zones*" using clustering techniques and feeds measured data to train ML models. The trained model is able to generalize the WDN structure and detect the presence of leakages in the zone, even in the case of untrained ones.
3. We assess the robustness of LEAKSTREAM under different placements of the leakage positions that were not present during the training phase.

In order to assess our results we use a simulation tool specifically tailored to match a WDN structure and collect the desired hydraulic measurements. Finally, we publicly released the dataset and the code implementation of the designed algorithm to allow repeatability and provide a performance benchmarking [2].

As shown in Fig. 1, a WDN consists of a series of interconnected links and nodes. Links represent pipes, while nodes comprise junctions, tanks, or reservoirs. Junctions are points that also function as demand points within the WDN. Tanks and reservoirs supply the hydraulic resources to the system, with tanks being finite water sources and reservoirs being infinite sources.

Due to the nature of WDNs, leakage characteristics tend to produce a similar impact in other collected measurements when positions are near. The goal of the proposed method is to detect leakages using only data collected from utility

Fig. 1. LoRaWAN and WDN network architecture.

meters, without relying on flow sensors placed along pipes to monitor internal hydraulic flows. Instead, we put the focus on monitoring hydraulic flows that exclusively exit from the network as utility sources (demand at the junction). This view is justified by the current trend where any utility will be served from a smart meter in the near future [3].

Specifically, LEAKSTREAM works in two steps: i) first use k-means to cluster the WDN junctions in groups or zone with similar features and ii) use a Neural Network to classify the zone based on the correctness of the dynamic flow as affected or not by leakage. The defined model is supported by current literature in [4] and [5]. The authors established a fixed node merge threshold to combine nodes exhibiting similar leakage traits in order to improve classifier accuracy. Differently, we consider fewer features, introduce stream processing and simplify the ML model.

Selected wireless network technology There is no one-size-fits-all wireless technology for leakage detection, with different solutions being better suited for various use cases. IoT chips with low power consumption and long-distance communication capability are ideal for these purposes. Three trends in communication have been identified: WiFi-based networks, cellular networks, and LPWAN networks. LPWAN devices are expected to dominate the field [6]. However, it faces potential scalability issues in large-scale scenarios. This study targets the LoRaWAN technology [7] and proposes to address scalability issues by enabling real-time analysis and processing of the vast amounts of data generated by connected devices within the network edge. By streamlining data processing, the network can achieve improved performance and better resource allocation, consequently addressing the challenges associated with large-scale deployments.

As shown in Fig. 1, the LoRaWAN architecture relies on a star-of-star topology, where End Devices (EDs) connect with one or more Gateways (GWs) that forward packets to the Network Server (NS) and eventually to the corresponding IoT applications server. According to the considered scenario, LoRaWAN EDs are deployed in the WDN to collect data from junction nodes (water demand). Moreover, we leverage NebulaStream [8], an IoT stream-processing framework to enable processing data at the edge, with the aim of reducing the latency and the traffic on the backhaul [9]. This latter part is represented in Fig. 1 where the resources processing happens at the gateways controlled by the NS, which also plays a role in the remote processing coordinator.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. The related work is in Section 2. In Section 3 we detail the proposed leakage detection approach. The

learning architecture, which represents the STREAMLEAK building blocks and the experimental setup is presented in Section 4, including the details of the stream processing design. Finally, the performance of the proposed approach is evaluated in Section 5. Conclusions are drawn in Section 6.

2 Related work

As for data-driven leakage detection techniques for WDNs the most widely used approaches in the literature are prediction-classification methods [10]. One notable study by [11] focuses on leak localization in WDNs using Bayesian classifiers. The authors provide a technique that takes into account sensor noise, leak size uncertainty and demand uncertainty to calibrate the probability density functions for pressure residuals. Using case studies from the Hanoi and Nova Icaria networks, they show how a Bayesian classifier operates in locating leaks in real-time.

Another approach presented by [12] addresses leakage zone identification in WDNs through an iterative method based on machine learning. To find leakage zones, Authors use a combination of k -means clustering and a random forest classifier. Through iterations, the method refines the identification process, reduces the number of candidate leakage zones, and selects the minimum number of sensors for training the model. Different approaches, such as Support Vector Machines (SVMs), Long short-term memory (LSTM) recurrent neural network [13], k -NN classifiers or multi-layer neural networks have been investigated in [14] and [15], respectively. Convolutional neural networks (CNN) can be used to learn the different pressure residual maps [16]. Moreover, K -means clustering was used to divide the network into different k zones based on the pressure residual matrix generated by the hydraulic model [17]. Most of the time these methods can not generalize the presence of leakage not considered during the training phase.

To consider the implementation of water leakage detection in a real WDN scenario, we face a high volume of data reaching the application server, which can be considered as a Big Data system. Cloud-based systems do not fully exploit IoT capabilities and present bottlenecks, while Fog-based solutions may lack resources when dealing with Big Data. Emerging distributed approaches balance processing operations by reducing data at the edge and performing more expensive computations in the cloud. This is achieved through mapping functions that aggregate local data and send only the results upstream. A large set of software frameworks have been designed or extended for dealing with this paradigm, among which Hadoop 2.0 [18], Spark [19] and Flink [20]. These frameworks are similar in terms of functionalities for optimizing the query process. NebulaStream is an example of a novel data processing platform that addresses heterogeneity, unreliability and scalability challenges in IoT systems. It includes an inference operator used from LEAKSTREAM to support edge processing.

3 Leakage detection problem

In our WDN hydraulic model we analyze the water flow using the Hardy-Cross method [21] that assumes that the water flow follows a distribution pattern where

Fig. 2. Considered WDN branch with 75 junctions and 1 reservoir (junctions and flow measurements).

every junction adheres to the principle of continuity. The continuity equation dictates that the algebraic sum of flow rates in pipes converging at a node, along with any external flows, must be zero. To better formulate the concept, we used pre-defined network model offered by Open Water Analytics’s community public repository [22]. Specifically, we considered the sub-networks shown in Fig. 2. The network provides $n = 75$ junctions and $m = 1$ reservoirs. Each node is configured with a specific *base demand* pattern which represents the water request of the user during the whole simulation changing at a step size of an hour. In WDNs, base demand and satisfied water requests are two distinct concepts related to the amount of water needed and the amount of water that can be successfully supplied to the consumers. In summary, while base demands represent the foreseen water consumption by users in a WDN, satisfied water request reflects the actual amount of water provided to them, taking into account the network’s capacity and available resources and is labelled as demand value. In the network representation of Fig. 2, we can see that, for a specific measurement interval, two color scales are used to plot nodes demand values (color of the circle marker), and pipes flow (color of the nodes connection segment). The reservoir is positioned on the left side of the network (element with 7384 identifier), with flow primarily moving from left to right. As we move further away from the reservoir, the total demand value and pressure at the junctions decrease due to the demand from left-side junctions.

Fig. 3 illustrates the average pressure and Fig. 3(b) the demand values experienced at each node in our selected network, respectively. The black line represents the measured values when no leaks are present in the network, with nodes sorted by their position relative to the reservoir; farther nodes perceive lower pressure and lower demand value. The two dashed lines demonstrate the impact of the presence of two leaks, respectively. The vertical dashed line provides cluster or zone separation.

Fig. 3. Average pressure in Pound per square inch [PSI] (a) and demand value in Gallons per minute [GPM] (b) of 75 WDN nodes in three different scenarios, one without leakage (line) and two with leakage at different positions (dashed lines).

The proposed approach focuses on establishing a ML model that captures the physical hydraulic inner properties governing the flow within the zone where only part of the base demand is satisfied. LEAKSTREAM considers clusters of nodes where leakage presence produces a similar effect independently from its position in the cluster. Thus, rather than considering multiple leakage positions to train the ML model, we consider the effect of a generic leakage in the network and we train the ML model to recognize it.

The approach first requires the creation of clusters of nodes according to the proximity position of the network and to the trend of the two features' pressure and demand value on the cluster nodes. Furthermore, these features are used to train the model. We assumed that leaks occur only at a pipe of the network and we expect to create a model for each cluster.

We use the Water Network Tool for Resilience (WNTR) simulator [23] in order to generate our desired hydraulic data. WNTR is a Python package designed to simulate the WDN. It takes into account the topological structure of the pipeline system along with a set of initial conditions (e.g. pipe diameter) and rules of how the system is operated so that it can compute flows and pressures throughout the network for a specific period of time. The simulator can add leaks to the network using a leak model [24].

4 LEAKSTREAM: distributed leakage detection

Our proposed approach relies on different entities. We use WNTR to generate a suitably large dataset to train and assess our ML model. The simulator generates a complete trace, with the status of each node and pipe over time. We then extract a subset of generated data, together with the actual status of nodes, and use that to train the ML model whose input is the total set of measurements in a period of time, and whose output is a vector with the status **leakage/no-leakage** of each cluster. In Fig. 4(a) we show the 2D data position of the clustering of the nodes extracted by the k-means algorithm, nodes belong-

Fig. 4. Map of the nodes and GWs position, nodes are coloured according to the selected clustering, GWs are provided together with the coverage area (a). Example of deployed operators that implement LEAKSTREAM on GWs workers.

ing to the same cluster are represented with the same color. We employ Elbow and Silhouette Methods to find the best k number of clusters. Both are based on empirical methods where inter and intra-clustering node similarity functions are applied to evaluate better k value. We pick a range of candidate values of k , then apply k -Means clustering using each of the values of k to extract the best number of clusters that is $k = 7$. Algorithm features include average demand value and pressure rather than the node's position, for this reason, in the figure, nodes belonging to the same cluster are not properly in proximity.

We integrate a Supervised Classification model in which we try to predict if there is a leakage on the cluster. Using a classical approach, we have been able to build a feature matrix \mathbf{X} and an output vector \mathbf{y} , suitable for being used for training and testing ML algorithms. We extract our training set (\mathbf{X} matrix) with the following features: **demand_value**, **pressure** and **position** measured in the network cluster (Cartesian coordinates are considered for the position). Since this is a classification problem, our test set (\mathbf{y} vector) contains just the Boolean **has_leak** field, reporting if that specific cluster is currently affected by a leak in some moment. We designed that the classifier takes as input features a matrix with $n \times t$ rows, and 4 columns, where n is the number of nodes present in the cluster and t the number of collected measures for each node in the considered time period. The classifier output is a vector with t number of elements that reports the prediction value for each reading interval. According to the provided input, the model can detect leakages at different intervals of time.

For the model definition, we consider a Neural Network with a densely connected hidden layer, a dropout layer to reduce overfitting, and an output sigmoid layer that returns the probability of a cluster being a leakage. We select 40 neurons for the hidden layer, evaluated by the 4×10 , the features and average

nodes per cluster respectively. Looking at the data distribution, for the training phase, we suppose that measures are collected hourly over a time period of 2 months, half part without leakage and half part with a single leakage with an average lost water flow rate of 0.05 GPM. We remark that the goal of the proposed approach is to use a single leakage position for each cluster to create a model able to generalize leakage detection at any position. Consequently, the total number of samples used is 10,080 ($7 \times 24 \times 60$, clusters, hours and day respectively). The result is a setup where positive examples contain a very low attendance rate. The produced dataset results are unbalanced with a value of 7.1% (720 : 10,080) of positive samples. Notice that the model is fitted using a batch size of 2048 samples which ensures that each batch has a good chance of containing a few positive samples. Thus, we set the output layer’s bias to help with initial convergence.

The application of the model has been compared in terms of accuracy on the cluster leakage classification. Accuracy values are calculated after the fitting and prediction phases and after the confusion matrices generation. Specifically, to generate the confusion matrix, we extract the *True Positives (TP)*, *True Negatives (TN)*, *False Positives (FP)* and *False Negatives (FN)* values. False negatives and false positives are samples that were incorrectly classified. True negatives and true positives are samples that were correctly classified. Finally, accuracy is the percentage of examples correctly classified ($Accuracy = (TP + TN)/(TP + TN + FP + FN)$).

4.1 Stream processing

LEAKSTREAM aims to reduce leakage detection latency by processing data at the edge and decreasing the amount of data transmitted over the network backhaul, thereby minimizing link latency to the central server. Different from the classical cloud paradigm, where data is gathered centrally for processing in a batch way. We propose to use sensor-fog-cloud scheme, which enables dynamic allocation of data stream processing across nodes from source to cloud. In this section, we present the implementation of the LEAKSTREAM algorithm based on the sensor-fog-cloud approach. In particular, we implement this approach in the *NebulaStream* platform [8].

According to the selected network topology, we find the best suitable GWs position to collect monitoring data. The considered GWs positions are shown in Fig. 4(a) (triangular markers are the nodes) together with the coverage area (represent by big blue circles). According to the coverage area, each GW is able to receive only a subset of the total WDN measurements.

NebulaStream allows the implementation of distributed queries by means of workers running on edge. As shown in Fig. 4(b), workers are responsible for moving the data flow hierarchically from source to sink, including the data sources, and applying different operators before forwarding the results in the output stream towards another worker or a data sink. The framework also includes a coordinator, running on the cloud, which exposes an interface for responding to external queries. For the LoRaWAN network, we consider the resource capabilities present in the GWs as our edge layer. The GWs run a proxy agent and use

it to feed the worker source. The activation by personalization method is configured in the LoRaWAN network to access the monitored information normally ciphered in the LoRaWAN protocol.

In Fig. 4(b), we depict blocks structure of our implementation, with a total of 2 workers (one for each GW). The figure also shows the operators that have been identified for data pre-processing and for supporting the algorithm. In the edge layer, the *source* operator connects the data stream and the *projection* operator for selecting a sub-group of data packet fields. Thus, the figure shows the *filter* operator, which is responsible for extracting all data referring to the same cluster and the infer model operator. The latter facilitates an inference procedure on the incoming data stream, requiring a pre-trained TensorFlow model provided through a function parameter. Lastly, at the cloud layer, classification results from network zones or clusters are consolidated. Subsequently, these results are forwarded to the application server, which is responsible for initiating the leakage alarm trigger. Finally, we also report the query, whose implementation in Java is summarized in the following code.

```

1 // Provide input parameter
2 String CLUSTER = ARG_PAR_1
3 List FEATURES_LIST = ARG_PAR_2
4 //create stream and select subset of fields
5 Query stream = new Query().from("WDN_STREAM")
6 stream.from(gatewaystream).project(FEATURES_LIST)
7     .filter(CLUSTER)
8     .inferModel(Objects.requireNonNull(
9         InferModel.class.getResourceAsStream("/model.tflite")))
10     .on(attribute(FEATURES_LIST)
11     .as(attribute("leakage_prediction", BasicType.FLOAT32)));
12     .sink(new MQTTSink());

```

5 Performance evaluation

In this section, we report the evaluation performance of the suggested method when varying leakage positions. For each cluster model, we merge together the dataset without leakage and the dataset with leakage, finally, we split it into the train, validation, and test sets. The test set is used at the end to evaluate how the model generalizes to new data. This is especially important with imbalanced datasets where overfitting is a significant concern from the lack of training data. We note that generating the training dataset, LEAKSTREAM considers a single leakage. To assess the impact of the chosen leakage position on the performance of the cluster model, Fig. 5 displays the accuracy of 9 different models (represented by different lines) in detecting the presence of 9 leakages located at 9 distinct positions within the same cluster. Each model has been trained by moving a single leakage around the pipes cluster. Specifically, Fig. 5(a) refers to cluster 3, and Fig. 5(b) refers to cluster 4 of the provided WDN. As can be noticed, the accuracy exceeds 95% in most of the cases. Clearly, system performance depends on the selected leakage position; for instance, in Fig. 5(b), model 6 achieves

Fig. 5. Accuracy results of 9 models to infer leakage at different positions for cluster 3 (a) and cluster 4 (b). Models are trained by considering leakage position in all the cluster.

an accuracy above 90% for all considered leakages positions except position 6, where the accuracy is 100% since this position was used to create the training and validation set of this model.

As demonstrated above, the choice of leakage position for the model creation can influence the final performance of the generated model, making it crucial to define an evaluation method for selecting the leakage position. LEAKSTREAM computes the leakage position by starting from the cluster's centre of gravity and finding the nearest pipe where the leakage is set. In case of no WDN topology information are accessible, LEAKSTREAM treats real collected demand value and pressure trend as reference behaviours and generates a dataset with leakage events by using the general curve fitting method. As for the model generalization we take into account a complete scenario where leakages that were not present during the training phases are added to the WDNs. To this aim, we consider 75

Cluster	Loss	Accuracy [%]	No leakage detected (TN)[%]	No leakage Incorrectly Detected (FP) [%]	Leakage Incorrectly Detected (FN) [%]	Leakage detected (TP) [%]
1	0.046	99.730	93.609	0.200	0.070	6.120
2	0.034	98.344	92.178	1.656	0.000	6.166
3	0.014	99.785	93.658	0.122	0.093	6.128
4	0.036	99.223	93.707	0.081	0.696	5.517
5	0.143	97.971	93.725	0.049	2.158	4.066
6	0.069	97.672	93.213	0.475	1.853	4.458
7	0.158	97.260	93.272	0.501	2.298	3.929
Average	0.071	98.569	93.338	0.441	1.024	5.198

Table 1. Average performance results at the different clusters in case of a dataset of time duration of two months. The first two columns report loss and accuracy, while the remaining 4 columns summarize the actual vs. predicted labels, where values are percentages of TN, FP, FN and TP with respect to the total number of observations.

additional test set. We set the leakage position in proximity to each node present in the cluster. Table 1 presents the accuracy outcomes of this case study, taking again into account the previous 7 clusters. The first two columns report loss and average accuracy for each cluster, while the remaining 4 columns summarize the actual vs. predicted labels, where values are reported as percentages of TN, FP, FN and TP with respect to the total number of observations. As noticed from the table, the lower performance of 97.67% and 97.26% are obtained from clusters 6 and 7, although the average accuracy for the other clusters is more than 98.5%. Evidently, the models' performance decreases, especially when clusters are far from the hydraulic source, this is the situation of clusters 5, 6 and 7. Indeed, according to the trend of demand value and pressure, in these clusters, the nodes perceive more fluctuation that keeps harder the detection of the model. However, the precision is nevertheless maintained at a good level for all the clusters.

Finally, we note that for extremely complicated networks, performance can be maintained at a high level by developing many models that work in a subpart of the WDN as more simply separated districts.

6 Conclusion

This paper introduces LEAKSTREAM, an innovative solution that enhances monitoring, leak management, and prediction in water distribution networks (WDNs) by leveraging stream processing within LPWAN networks, specifically focusing on LoRaWAN. The system utilizes IoT-based water sensors and machine learning algorithms to detect leaks at the network edge. The proposed method has been demonstrated to be robust, capable of identifying leaks even with incomplete or inaccurate information about the collected measurements from the entire WDN. Through simulations, the approach achieved an average accuracy of 99.2% for detecting nearby leakages and 97.6% for identifying leaks farther away from the hydraulic source. Furthermore, this approach does not rely on having complete knowledge of the WDN's topology and only requires data from normal smart meter operation behaviour.

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